

MEDICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CORRECTION OF ANXIETY DISORDERS AFTER COVID-19 INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article is devoted to the widespread anxiety disorders in patients who have undergone COVID-19 and their psychocorrection. The main focus of the article is on the comparative study of the effectiveness of various integrative psychocorrection methods in eliminating these post-infectious mental states.

The study evaluates the clinical value of Cognitive-Behavioral Psychotherapy (CBP) and the modern Mindfulness approach, along with traditional psychopharmacotherapy (PPT). The article describes methodological approaches to assess the impact of each intervention method on the mental well-being of patients..

Relevance. Today, it is known that the SARS-CoV-2 COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic has affected not only the physical health of patients, but also their mental state, leading to an exacerbation of existing mental illnesses and the emergence of new ones.

The main behavioral changes resulting from stress include anxiety, irritability, apathy, depression, decreased ability to solve problems, slowness of movement, smoking, alcohol abuse, etc.

Symptoms of anxiety or depression due to stress associated with the COVID-19 pandemic were observed in approximately 31% of patients in the United States.

Many researchers in their works directly link the causes of the development of mental illnesses in the COVID-19 clinic with stress factors, while other authors indicate in their works neurological diseases caused by COVID-19 and the consequences of organic pathology of the brain. In particular, approximately 36.4% of patients with COVID-19 had neurological diseases, including severe viral hemorrhagic encephalitis, toxic encephalopathy, acute cerebrovascular accident, and others. Despite numerous studies on the study of mental disorders in COVID-19, the issues of their pathogenesis still remain unclear and controversial. This requires a deeper study of this topic.

The aim of the study is to study and evaluate the effectiveness of the integrative psychocorrection method in eliminating anxiety disorders after COVID-19 infection.

Research materials and methods. The study was conducted on 142 patients diagnosed with and treated for Covid-19 infection. The cohort consisted of patients aged 18-48 years, of

whom 46% (n=65) were men and 54% (n=77) were women. The average age of the subjects was 29+10.5.

The study was conducted in two stages. In the first stage, the psycho-emotional state of patients diagnosed with COVID-19 infection before psychotherapy was diagnosed.

In the second stage, the psycho-emotional state indicators were reassessed by using psychotherapeutic correction in combination with standard therapy, psychopharmacotherapy and psychotherapy. For the purpose of psychocorrection, cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy and Mindfulness were used in the main group of patients, and only the CBT method was used in the 1st comparison group.

In order to compare and evaluate the effectiveness of the applied psychotherapy and psychopharmacotherapy, the study groups were formed as follows:

1) the main group consisted of 48 patients, and in order to determine the effectiveness of psychotherapy, standard treatment, PFT, as well as CBT and Mindfulness were used; 2) The comparison group was divided into two: in comparison group No. 1, 47 patients received standard treatment, CBT, and only cognitive-behavioral psychotherapy (CBT), and in comparison group No. 2, 47 patients received only psychopharmacotherapy along with standard treatment.

For an objective assessment of anxiety disorders in dynamics, the HADS (Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale), which is widely used in clinical practice, was used.

Anxiolytic drugs used for psychopharmacotherapy were selected individually for each patient.

Psychotherapy was carried out from the first day of the medical-psychological examination. Psychotherapeutic interviews were conducted with patients once every 3-4 days, and 6-8 times over 30 days, taking into account the patient's condition. 2 of the interviews were conducted in inpatient conditions, and the rest were conducted on an outpatient basis, using individual techniques for each patient.

Results. When analyzing the clinical expression of anxiety in patients using the HADS questionnaire, according to the general indicators before treatment, 37 (77.1%) patients in the main group had clinically expressed anxiety ($11 \leq$ points), 6 (12.5%) respondents had subclinical anxiety (8-10 points), and 5 (10.4%) had normal indicators (0-7 points).

In the 1st comparison group, 37 (78.7%) patients had clinically expressed anxiety ($11 \leq$ points), 7 (14.9%) respondents had subclinical anxiety (8-10 points), and 3 (6.4%) had normal indicators (0-7 points).

In the 2nd comparison group, 37 (78.7%) patients had clinically pronounced anxiety ($11 \leq$ points), 7 (14.9%) subjects had subclinical anxiety (8-10 points), and 3 (6.4%) had normal indicators (0-7 points) (Table 1).

Table 1

Pre-treatment clinical indicators of anxiety symptoms according to the HADS questionnaire in patients in the main group

p	Хавоти		Асосий гуруҳ		1-таққослаш гуруҳи (n=47)		2-таққослаш гуруҳи (n=47)	
	(n=48)							
	abc	%	abc	%	abc	%	abc	%
	

Клини к ифодаланга н хавотир	37	1	77,1±6,	37	0	78,7±6,	37	0	78,7±6,
Субкли ник хавотир	6	8	12,5±4,	7	2	14,9±5,	7	2	14,9±5,
Хавоти р йўқ (норма)	5	5	10,4±4,	3		6,4±3,6	3		6,4±3,6

According to the data presented in the table above, in our study, the clinical and relatively subclinical course of anxiety in patients diagnosed with COVID-19 infection predominated.

After the above-mentioned medical and psychological correction methods, the clinical expression of anxiety and depression in patients was re-analyzed using the HADS questionnaire. According to the questionnaire, clinically expressed anxiety (11≤ points) in the main group of respondents was initially 37 (77.1%), but after psychocorrection (1 month) it was noted in 8 (16.7%) patients. Subclinical anxiety was initially detected in 6 (12.5%) respondents, and after psychocorrection in 11 (22.9%) respondents (8-10 points). Before psychocorrection, normal indicators were detected in 5 (10.4%) in this group, and after treatment, normal indicators (0-7 points) were noted in 19 (39.6%) respondents.

Clinically expressed anxiety in 37 (78.7%) of patients in comparison group 1 initially and in 23 (48.9%) after PFT and PT; subclinical anxiety in 7 subjects (14.9%) before psychocorrection and 17 subjects (36.2%) after treatment; the normal level of anxiety was noted in 3 (6.4%) respondents at first, and in 7 (14.9%) respondents after psychocorrection.

37 (78.7%) of the respondents in the comparison group had clinically expressed anxiety at baseline and 32 (68.1%) after treatment; subclinical anxiety in 7 subjects (14.9%) before psychocorrection and 10 subjects (21.3%) after treatment; Normal anxiety indicators were initially recorded in 3 patients (6.4%), and after psychocorrection in 5 patients (10.6%) (Table 2).

Table 2

Clinical indicators of anxiety symptoms after treatment according to the HADS questionnaire in the main group of patients

Хавоти р	Асосий гуруҳ (n=48)		1-таққослаш гуруҳи (n=47)		2-таққослаш гуруҳи (n=47)	
	абс	%	абс	%	абс	%
Клини к ифодаланга н хавотир	8	16,7±5,	23	48,9±7,	32	68,1±6,
Субкли ник хавотир	11	22,9±6,	17	36,2±7,	10	21,3±6,

р (норма)	Хавоти йўқ	19	39,6±7,	7	2	14,9±5,	5	5	10,6±4,
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Based on the above data, statistically significant positive dynamics were noted in all indicators in the main group of respondents. In particular, in the main group of patients who used PFT, CBP and Mindfulness, the number of subclinical and normal indicators increased due to a decrease in the level of clinically expressed anxiety.

Conclusion. Identifying anxiety in patients with COVID-19 helped to mitigate long-term mental health consequences and improve the quality of life of patients by reducing the risk of chronic psychological distress.

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